

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS THE VOICE CATEGORY OF VERB IN MODERN RUSSIAN LINGUISTICS

Khasanova S.K.

Navoi branch of PROFI UNIVERSITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13333200>

Abstract. *In the 19th and 20th centuries, Russian linguists significantly increased their research on verbs and their categories. Russian linguists conducted extensive studies on the structural and comparative aspects of verbs and their translation, including the category of voice and its types. This article provides an in-depth analysis of the contributions and research results of these scholars to Russian linguistics.*

Keywords: *grammar, voice category, linguistic analysis, systemic-structural and communicative-functional factors.*

In the 19th century, K.S. Aksakov recognized the need for a new approach to the study of the voice category of verb in Russian language and proposed that comparative analysis could serve as the main solution in this area. Of course, the comparative method plays some role in the analysis of any grammatical category. However, K.S. Aksakov suggested making the comparative approach as the primary focus when distinguishing verb voices. The scholar contrasted voice verb formed with the suffix "-ся" against those formed without such a suffix. Aksakov's works note that verb voices formed without the suffix should be considered as definite and intermediate voices.

Taking into consideration that K.S. Aksakov was primarily a philosopher, publicist, poet, and literary critic, it is not surprising that he focused on the formal aspects in his interpretation of verb voices. Indeed, the idea that semantic aspects should be emphasized in the study of verb voices, which is fundamentally correct, has been highlighted above.

From the mid-19th century, the issue of bringing grammar closer to spoken language was brought to the forefront in Russian linguistics and was considered one of the pressing issues. This was because linguistic theory, without connections to spoken language, would turn into a collection of just writings or thoughts. "Popularizing" grammar, or interpreting it in alignment with spoken language, was believed to help theoretical knowledge be effectively applied in practice. Such approaches in linguistics also influenced the study and teaching of verb voices. Works with this perspective can be found in the research of leading Russian linguists such as V.I. Dal, F.F. Fortunatov, A.A. Potebnya, A.A. Shakhmatov, V.V. Vinogradov, A.M. Peshkovsky, and N.P. Nekrasov. For instance, V.I. Dal suggested categorizing verbs into two types: direct (non-repetitive) and repetitive. He criticized the formal approach to distinguishing verb voices, arguing that verbs formed with the suffix "-ся" could take any voice form in speech.

In fact, V.I. Dal encountered the inadequacy of theoretical conclusions about verb voices while preparing the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language." Therefore, in the preface to the dictionary, he drew public attention to this issue and proposed specific solutions. When highlighting the confusion related to verb voices in earlier dictionaries, Dal emphasized that these errors were not merely coincidental. He explained that the confusion resulted from shortcomings in the theory of verb voices and mistakes in their systematization. In the preface, Dal mentioned that it was more appropriate to make decisions based on the speech context rather than categorizing verbs into specific voice forms. These thoughts of the linguist

were highly effective in the matter of distinguishing verb voices and served as an important methodological basis in subsequent linguistic studies. For example, N.P. Nekrasov shared similar conclusions about verb voices with V.I. Dal.

At the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th centuries, F.F. Fortunatov's research marked a new era in the study of verb voices in Russian language. His article "Verb Voices in Russian Language" can be considered a significant scientific achievement of its time. This article clarified and systematized the thoughts on verb voices in Russian language up to the early 20th century. According to S. Karsevsky, "F.F. Fortunatov substantiated N. Nekrasov's ideas about reflexive verbs transforming transitive verbs into intransitive ones and initiated a new stage in Russian linguistics' study of verb voices." Fortunatov's views on verb voices were based on the comparison of grammatical forms and their meanings. He noted that it is impossible to analyze verb voices formed without the suffix "-ся" in speech since they cannot be compared and, therefore, cannot possess a distinct meaning.

Overall, Fortunatov's ideas about verb voices, especially reflexive verbs, differed from his predecessors by focusing more on morphological features and their content. His research on the relationship between the agent and the action, and the influence of voice categories on verb compatibility, positively impacted the subsequent study of verb voices.

A.A. Potebnya's research also played a significant role in the study of voice forms in Russian linguistics. According to Potebnya, no verb in Russian language can simultaneously express multiple voice meanings. He stated, "When a verb transitions from one voice to another, the previous voice meaning is not preserved in any way. We see a verb that has adopted multiple voice forms but retains the meaning of only one". This situation is similar to the stacking of voice meanings in a single verb in Uzbek language. In Uzbek, several voice forms with specific grammatical shapes can manifest in a single verb. These voice forms appear in the order of reflexive, causative, passive, and cooperative voices. Although a word that has adopted all voice forms rarely appears in Uzbek spoken language, theoretically, such a word can be created. In this case, the verb will adopt the meaning of the last voice form added. Potebnya's views suggest a similar idea for Russian.

Potebnya believed that the concept of voice in Russian lives in spoken language and only makes sense when applied in speech processes. Additionally, verb voices indicate the relationship between the subject and predicate, and sometimes between the object and predicate. Thus, Potebnya said, "Dividing verbs into objective and subjective types serves as the basis for defining voices." These views, specific to Russian language and its characteristics, are reasonable.

Another prominent Russian scholar, A.A. Shakhmatov's views on verb voices and their characteristics fully align with Fortunatov's ideas. Shakhmatov stated, "Forms derived from a single verb, reflecting different relationships between the action and the agent, such as the state of the agent towards the action, are considered verb voices". He emphasized that morphology studies the suffixes forming verb voices. Indeed, verb voices in Uzbek language also appear as a grammatical category expressing various relationships between the agent and the action. For instance, the cooperative voice form indicates that the action is performed by more than one person or entity, while the reflexive voice shows actions performed by the subject upon itself. Each voice meaning divides into smaller subgroups. The realization of specific grammatical meanings of verb voices will be discussed in later chapters.

In contemporary Russian linguistics, the integration of systemic-structural and communicative-functional factors has become predominant. The results of lexical-semantic research demand the identification of new systems encompassing various linguistic units and their interrelationships. The following perspective is relevant in this context: "The continuous development of linguistic semantics necessitates the delineation of the roles of systems, structures, and forms in the comprehensive understanding of language and speech."

The increasing importance of functional grammar in Russian linguistics, along with reliance on the principles of functional-semantic fields, has also transformed the perspectives on verb voices. Naturally, this required theoretical clarity on what functional-semantic fields are and how elements are positioned within them.

Key issues that linguists need to address include the extent to which elements contribute to forming the voice category of verbs, their impact on transitivity and intransitivity, and their compatibility with affirmative or negative verbs. These factors determine whether elements are positioned at the core, periphery, or edge of the field. The complexity of the voice category must also be considered by linguists, as "the category of voice is not merely a linguistic phenomenon indicating the relationship between the object and the subject (since the presence of an action and its performer naturally establishes a relationship between the object and the subject). This category is significant in terms of its influence on the semantic relationships between the object and the subject."

It becomes evident that specialists in Russian grammar are currently more interested in understanding precisely how verb voices contribute to the relationships between an action and its performer. Overall, "the elements of voices can be viewed as a set within a functional-semantic field. In this process, the semantic relationship conveyed through the action expressed by the verb and its performer can be of crucial importance."

In recent years, the practice of comparative research on the verb voice category has been developing in Russian linguistics. This is due to the complexity of the voice category in Russian, and comparative analysis with analogous grammatical units in other languages can help resolve some unresolved issues. One such work includes A.A. Kotiyeva's thoughts on the classification of verb voices and verb conjugation in modern Russian and English. As a result of her analysis, the researcher concludes: "Verb voices in English and Russian can be divided into active and passive types. Verb voices are a grammatical category that determines whether the subject is represented by a pronoun or noun and whether the subject performs or receives the action." From the perspective of the impact of voice forms on verb conjugation, the researcher's views are quite reasonable.

T.S. Shmeleva approached the typological study of verb voices from a linguosemiotic perspective. According to the researcher, "the category of verb voice is problematic and unresolved in all languages. At the same time, this category is a phenomenon that exists in almost all languages of the world." From this standpoint, the researcher acknowledges the vast opportunities for studying verb voices. In her research, T.S. Shmeleva analyzes the linguosemiotic aspects of constructions involving verb voices in English, Russian, German, and other languages. Analyzing factual materials, she concludes that voice constructions, like other linguistic units, possess symbolic characteristics. Overall, this study can serve as a foundation for further research related to the more detailed classification of verb voices.

Research that separately examines the elements forming the category of verb voice also plays a crucial role in uncovering the essence of the issue. For example, L.V. Staroduseva analyzed the intermediate voice in English and the problems encountered in its translation into Russian. As noted, verb voices are inherently complex, and therefore, issues arise in their translation. When translating verb voices from one language to another, the process does not always occur through equivalent grammatical categories. In some cases, translation transformation is observed. Therefore, the significance of research related to the translation of grammatical categories is increasing. This is also relevant for collecting information necessary for automatic translation programs. In this regard, studies analyzing the translation of verb voices in Uzbek into other languages and vice versa are also important.

In conclusion, the analysis of verb voices in Russian language shows that initially, the voice category was studied from a formal perspective. In this stage, the classification of verb voices was primarily based on the suffixes used to form them. From the mid-19th century, attention in Russian linguistics began to shift to the lexical-semantic characteristics of constructions and the influence of verb combinability. In other words, the semantic characteristics of verbs took a central role in grouping verb voices. In modern Russian linguistics, verb voices began to be analyzed from the perspective of the functional-semantic field. This type of analysis relied on various bases for the placement of grammatical category elements within the field. Factors such as the frequency of use of verb voices, their impact on verb semantics, and combinability abilities are among these bases. The multifaceted nature of verb voices and the differences in their characteristics across various languages underscore the importance of comparative-typological research. Such studies contribute to improving the quality of their translation into different languages.

REFERENCES

1. Great Russian Encyclopedia: in 35 volumes. Volume 1. – Moscow: Great Russian Encyclopedia, 2005. – p. 457. 766 pages.
2. Bondarenko A.V. (ed.). Problems of Functional Grammar. Field Structures. – Saint Petersburg: Nauka, 2005. – p. 10. 480 pages.
3. Dal V.I. Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language: in 4 parts. – Moscow: Society of Lovers of Russian Literature, 1863. – 627 pages.
4. Karcevski S. System of the Russian Verb. Thesis. Dissertation. – Prague, 1927. – p. 82. 184 pages.
5. Kotieva A.A. Classification of Voice and Mood in Modern English and Russian Languages // Scientific-Educational Journal for Students and Teachers StudNet No.11, 2020. – pp. 171-174.
6. Nekrasov N.P. On the Meaning of Forms of the Russian Verb. – Saint Petersburg: I. Paulson & Co, 1865. – 319 pages.
7. Potebnya A.A. From Notes on Russian Grammar. – Moscow - Leningrad, 1941. – pp. 2-5. 341 pages.
8. Salyakhova Z.I. Main Concepts of Studying Voice Issues in Linguistics // World of Science, Culture, Education. No.6 (31), 2011. – pp. 284-287.
9. Starodubtseva L.V. The Middle Voice in English Grammar and Features of Its Translation // Modern High-Tech Technologies. 2013. No.7-1. – pp. 87-88.

10. Theory of Functional Grammar. Personality. Voice / ed. A.V. Bondarko. – Saint Petersburg: Nauka, 1991. – p. 128. 369 pages.
11. Khamraeva M. The Category of Voice in Russian, Uzbek, and English Languages // Theory of Recent Scientific Research, 2022. No.3. – p. 2.
12. Shakhmatov A.A. Outline of the Modern Russian Literary Language. – Moscow: Uchpedgiz, 1941. – p. 167. 288 pages.
13. Shmeleva T.S. Typology of Voice Constructions: Lingosemiotic Aspect: Abstract of PhD Dissertation in Philological Sciences. – Izhevsk, 2012. – p. 3. 25 pages.